

Dellingr Phase 2: DO4

User authentication, authorization and accounting

Dellingr team *

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1 Executive Summary

The NeIC Dellingr project is investigating how a lightweight framework for sharing High Performance Computing (HPC) resources ¹ can be implemented between participating countries ². The resources will be open to eligible researchers ³ from the participating countries who wish to access resources in other participating countries. A feature of this resource sharing includes the case where the computing project is performed in an HPC center outside the home country of the researcher.

The AAI for the Tryggve and Glenna projects follows the requirements of their respective project members to authenticate and authorize users and do not attempt to set up an AAI scheme acceptable across all Service Providers.

In this document it is seen that the national providers of e-infrastructure have their own methods for authenticating both national and extra-national users. The Authorization schemes are technically compatible but not operationally compatible in that they require different sets of information to be present and the information shared is used differently.

EU regulations concerning authentication and identification are in place, but not yet technically implemented, that will help the authentication of users across national borders. For example, the technical bridge between eIDAS and eduGAIN will enable users to present a strong academic identity across borders. In the future, collaborating System Providers need to have international agreements and common policies regarding sharing user information in order to comply with GDPR and other regulations.

2 Outline of document

This document consists of the following sections:

- **Executive Summary**
- **Purpose of the document** Defines the scope of the deliverable and its intended audience.
- **Authentication** outlines the federated authentication systems used by service providers and how these are integrated to interfederations such as eduGAIN.
- **Authorization** describes how HPC access and resources are granted to users.
- **Accounting** describes how resource usage is monitored.

¹Defined generally as compute, network and storage e-infrastructure.

²Currently this includes the Nordic countries and Estonia.

³At the moment we do not address commercial users that some countries have agreements to provide/use resources.

- **AAI for the Dellingr framework** describes the requirements for sharing and group management in the Dellingr project.
- **AAI for NeIC Tryggve** describes the current status of AAI for Tryggve.
- **AAI for NeIC Glenna** describes the current status of AAI for Glenna.
- **EU law** outlines EU directives and regulations related to user authentication, authorization and accounting, as well as network and information security, and their implications to the Dellingr project.
- **Recommendations** lists recommendations by the Dellingr team.

3 Purpose of the Document

This document is to be used as a basis for further discussions on HPC resource sharing with the intent of leading to a general agreement.

3.1 Intended recipients

The intended recipients of this document are:

The National Providers of e-infrastructure and NeIC.

4 Authentication

The use of federated identities is very common nowadays. In the context of high-performance computing, accounts are created locally in supercomputers. However, the accounts are usually not created by hand, but based on the information provided by the users home organization (e.g. university). This information is transferred between the home organization and the service provider using federated identities. These are useful, because they automate the account creation process. If an automated process is not available for a set of users, service providers identify the users according to their policy and create local accounts. However, this manual process is more laborious and often also less trustful than use of federated identities.

An identity federation may be national i.e. the institutes within a country agree to share a set of authentication attributes. In a similar fashion, an identity federation may be international e.g. eduGAIN [1].

4.1 Denmark

Denmark uses WAYF [2] identities for users of WAYF member organizations and a manual process for other users. In the manual process, organization membership is validated based on the existence of an institutional email address.

4.1.1 Scope

WAYF has about 60 identity providers (IdPs), counting all universities and university colleges; most business academies and maritime schools; a few other orgs; and the national Danish ID for citizens and employees.

4.1.2 Technology

WAYF uses SAML2.

4.1.3 Federations

WAYF is compatible with eduGAIN.

4.2 Estonia

Estonia is using three main federations of identities for granting access to users:

- TaaT [3] – federation of mostly university and educational service providers.
- TARA – eIDAS-compliant broker service providing authentication with national eID, bank link and eIDAS identities.
- eduGAIN - production profiles.

In exceptional cases users cannot use identities from any of the federations above local username/password can be generated.

4.2.1 Scope

TaaT covers 20 IdPs, including largest academical institutions in Estonia.

TARA covers all citizens and residents in Estonia, as well as foreign nationals via eIDAS network (at the moment of writing limited to Germany, Belgium, Portugal, Italy and Spain).

4.2.2 Technology

TaaT and eduGAIN are using SAML, TARA is OpenID Connect based.

4.2.3 Federations

TaaT federates to eduGAIN. TARA federates to eIDAS.

4.3 Finland

Finland uses Haka [4] identities for users of higher education institutions. A manual process is used for other users. In the manual process, organization membership is validated based on the existence of and institutional email address. In autumn 2019, the possibility to use Virtu [5] identities will be offered for users of state research institutes.

4.3.1 Scope

All higher education institutions are members of Haka federation and, at the time of writing, six state research institutes have joined Virtu. Integration of more state research institutes into Virtu is underway.

4.3.2 Technology

Both Haka and Virtu use SAML2.

4.3.3 Federations

Haka is compatible with eduGAIN. Virtu would technically be compatible, but as Virtu is not meant for higher education institutions, it will not be integrated to eduGAIN.

4.4 Iceland

Each user is created manually and has to send in an ssh-key to gain access. In the manual process, organization membership is validated based on the existence of an institutional email address.

4.4.1 Technology

No federated access method is in use for access to HPC resources. WAYF authentication is used for software licences and eduroam etc.

4.5 Norway

In Norway, Feide [6] is the one common federation for public education and research.

4.5.1 Scope

The Feide federation is operated on an opt-in basis, so institutions must join explicitly. Feide is open to all higher and lower education institutions in Norway, as well as research centers. Therefore the entire academic sector is covered. There are no institutes explicitly excluded, apart from those that have not joined the Feide federation.

4.5.2 Technology

SAML [7] is the main protocol in Feide, and this is the interface used towards eduGAIN. There is also the possibility to use OAuth2 [8] and OpenID Connect [9].

4.5.3 Federations

Feide is a member of eduGAIN. However, since Feide is opt-in, that means Feide cannot be used to access a service connected via eduGAIN unless the corresponding home organization approves it beforehand. This restriction applies only to Feide as an Identity Provider. Services connected to Feide and published to eduGAIN can have their own criteria on whether they allow users to access them via other identity providers from eduGAIN or not.

4.6 Sweden

Sweden uses SWAMID [10] for national users from universities, university colleges, research institutions and government agencies. Today there is no federated access for non-national users. This is due to the fact that eduGAIN does not require identification of users on a level corresponding to SWAMID assurance level 2 [11]. Until The SWAMID/eduGAIN assurance level is in place, non-national users will have to verify their identity using a signed copy of their passport in order to have local username and password created.

4.6.1 Scope

SWAMID includes most universities, university colleges, research institutions and government agencies that are related to Swedish research and educational sector. SWAMID is operated by the national research and educational network SUNET.

4.6.2 Technology

SWAMID uses SAML2.

4.6.3 Federations

No. ⁴

4.7 Kalmar2

The Kalmar2 e-identity Union [12] was a pan-Nordic infrastructure formed by the identity federation members HAKA in Finland, Feide in Norway, WAYF in Denmark and SWAMID in Sweden for authentication and authorization of end users.

Entities participating in Kalmar2 were required to support SAML 2.0 as specified by OASIS. Furthermore, Kalmar2 specified a deployment profile defining how to configure the SAML 2.0 entities.

The Kalmar2 entities also had to follow the Interoperable SAML 2.0 Web Browser SSO Deployment Profile and in order to avoid conflicting IDs, each participating federation (country) was required to ensure that all participating entities have an SAML2.0 EntityID in a controlled namespace. The Kalmar2 federation was superseded by eduGAIN in 2017.

4.8 GÉANT Services

4.8.1 eduGAIN

The eduGAIN [1] inter-federation service connects identity federations around the world, simplifying access to content, services and resources for research and education communities. eduGAIN [1] was proposed and developed by the GÉANT [13] research and education networking community in Europe. The development was initiated in the GÉANT 2 Project, followed up in the successor GÉANT 3 project. In 2011, eduGAIN became an operational service.

eduGAIN provides an infrastructure for establishing trusted communications between users' identity providers and hosting service providers in different participating federations. The users authenticate at their home identity providers and obtain access to service providers. Technically, eduGAIN is managed by aggregating and distributing signed SAML 2.0 metadata files.

4.8.2 eduroam

The eduroam [14] global service enables students, researchers and staff from participating institutions to obtain internet connectivity across their local campus and also when visiting other participating

⁴Discussions are ongoing to federate with eduGAIN

institutions. The user authentication is handled by their home institution and authorization by the visited institution, eduroam also allows academics and researchers from participating institutions to go to any other participating institution and access the internet via the local network by virtue of their federated identity authenticated through the eduGAIN federation.

The eduroam service is a good example of a strong identity delegated by an external source. The hosting organization accepts that the authentication via eduGAIN of the user identity is “strong enough” to allow them to use their local e-infrastructure, in this case only the network. eduroam can also be found in the non-academic domain as some airports provide the service, cutting down on their effort to authenticate users themselves.

4.9 MyAcademicID

The MyAcademicID project [15], led by the European University Foundation, focuses primarily on developing a European Student electronic IDentity (eID) for higher education. This will allow students to identify and register themselves electronically at higher education institutions when going abroad on exchange and to access different student services.

The European Student eID for Higher Education will be the result of the integration of eduGAIN and the European Student Identifier and the establishment of digital bridges between them and the eIDAS [16] interoperability framework.

This effort is of importance to the Dellingr project and the subject of sharing e-infrastructure in the Nordic region as a requirement for a user to present a strong identity (see Section 4.6) is a must.

5 Authorization

A user can authenticate themselves (strongly or otherwise) but the permission (Authorization) to utilize a resource is not necessarily automatically granted. Authorization rests with the provider of the hosting e-infrastructure resource. Even if a user is accessing a non-local e-infrastructure resource within their own country, the Authorization rests with the hosting provider.

One of the statements of the Dellingr project is “The project is not intended to change the processes by which the national providers manage, allocate or otherwise support the national research priorities, including acquisition and operations.” Each country has an evaluation process for computing resource requests, normally ranging from more inquisitive to less for large to small projects respectively. The Authorization to proceed and use e-infrastructure resources is based on these national assessments. The sharing of e-infrastructure resources on the scale of the Dellingr project tends towards the lower range of the scale. A proposed Authorization scheme, encompassing the national schemes, is to be tested in the second test of a resource-sharing framework and will be presented in

a later Dellingr deliverable document. The goal is to derive an "hand-shake" part of the protocol that would allow getting access to resources with a single request from a user.

In order that national Authorization infrastructures can make a decision, a Nordic Authorization scheme should collect the following data for Authorization purposes:

- Organization details (see organization details below);
- PI data (see user details below);
- Project name, description, max lifetime;
- Co-workers data;
- Planned applications for use (0 or more);
- Explicit agreement with Terms of Services of a target service;
- OECD science domain code of the planned usage (required by some of the Nordic e-infras, e.g. CSC).

Where the organization details consist of the following:

- Organization name;
- Country;
- Type of organization (research, private, public etc);
- Funding mechanism - i.e. how organization is intending to cover usage of the resources. Can be by payment, through preliminary agreements etc.
- Planned type of usage;

The user (PI and co-workers) data, for Authorization purposes, consists of a choice of one or more of:

- Citizen of the same country that resource belongs to;
- EU/EEA Citizen;
- Citizen from outside the EU;
- Citizen of sanctioned country.

Getting the data above should allow service provider to make a decision about granting access to resources without asking for additional details from the requester.

6 Accounting

The usage of national e-infrastructure resources must be accounted for usage and provisioning purposes. The allocation of national e-infrastructure is made in core-hours, billing units or expressions of a resource value. The allocation limits may be enforced by local batch queueing or similar systems. Each national provider collects the accounting information through their own channels, automatically or manually.

For the Dellingr resource sharing, the important aspect of the accounting is to receive the accounting information in a timely manner to a central place. In the resource-sharing first pilot, this information was collected manually and entered to a NeIC wiki page [17]. For the second test of a resource-sharing framework a script to collect the accounting information from the Slurm [18] workload managers installed at many HPC sites. This accounting information is to be centralized to the resource sharing framework and this work will be presented in a later Dellingr deliverable document.

7 AAI for the Dellingr framework

7.1 Requirements for sharing

The Dellingr framework aims at proving access to services owned or operated by certain organizations (defined below as Service Providers) to users that are affiliated with other organizations (defined below as Service Consumers).

In order to be able to validate eligibility of access and establish trust between the entities, the following requirements have been identified:

- A high level of assurance of information and assertions passed in digital format;
- The ability for Service Providers to receive information about data of the Service Consumer (aka Primary Investigator) and all of the connected users. In particular, personal data is required. For access to some resources, citizenship info of the Service Consumers is required;
- The ability for Service Providers to receive information about affiliation of the Service Consumer. In particular, type of organization they belong to (private/public/...) is required.

Furthermore, as collaboration in practice involves contractual obligations, agreements to terms of services and delegation of responsibility, authorization system is required that would support these trust services in cross-border scenarios. The decision to by a Service Provider to authorize Service Consumer to use resources rests with the Service Provider. Therefore, the Authorization systems of the Service Providers should support these trust services in cross-border scenarios.

7.2 Group management

National HPC access and resources are commonly granted to projects, not individuals. Projects are groups of users who work towards the same objective and share the same resources. The current federated identity systems are missing information about groups, so projects cannot be handled in a federated way.

There are federated group services available for project management. Examples are Grouper, GÉANT Eduteams [19], Cesnet Perun [20] and Indico IAM [21]. Norway's Sigma2 Metacenter Administration System [22] also handles group information in a federated fashion.

Apart from the basic user grouping capabilities, it is common to expect group management solutions to support roles (for enabling role-based access control on connected services), hierarchy - to be able to express more complicated relationships, e.g. department's inclusion into university. Furthermore, for the sharing and accounting part, project level is a natural choice for storing limits and usage of a certain resource.

While in some basic cases group information can be embedded into the digital assertion of Identity Provider (e.g. role within a corresponding Identity Provider), for almost all practical cases an external group management service is needed.

As the needs for such service are not unique to Nordics, learning and being compliant with umbrella activities, for example, AEGIS⁵ - a continuation of EU-funded AARC1/2 projects.

8 AAI for NeIC Tryggve

The goal of Tryggve AAI task is to support adoption of Elixir AAI in Nordic countries. The most essential result so far is implementation of Elixir AAI multi-factor authentication in one web server in Oslo. Otherwise all Tryggve partners have different AAI practices and the project does not require harmonization of them.

9 AAI for NeIC Glenna

The goal of Glenna and Glenna 2 projects is to create a distributed Nordic cloud infrastructure, where users can do their computations and manage their data. The computations are done where the data is located, which reduces unnecessary moving of the data. Until April 2017, Glenna used Kalmar2 e-identity union, and after it, it has used eduGAIN.

One important challenge in the project is to integrate a group management service so that projects and resources could be managed centrally. There are several third-party projects, e.g. Cesnet Perun,

⁵ <https://aarc-project.eu/about/aegis/>

that provide SAML-based group management services. One aim of the Glenna 2 project is to test such a service for actual resource sharing.

10 EU law

As stated in Section 7.1 the aim of the Dellingr framework is to provide access to services, owned or operated by Service Providers, to Service Consumers. In order to do so, information on the Service Consumers at least to the extent outlined in Section 5 must be collected. The Dellingr framework will need to ensure the identity and eligibility of the Service Consumers as indicated in Sections 4 and 5, and also act as an intermediary to facilitate access to a number of services provided by the Service Providers.

The requirements mentioned above for the Dellingr framework are to some extent governed by the following regulations and directives ⁶.

- Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union. (NIS Directive [23])
- Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC. (eIDAS regulation [16])
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation [24]).

The **NIS Directive** affects Dellingr in that the Dellingr resource pool is considered as being a cloud service in the eyes of this directive:

Cloud computing services span a wide range of activities that can be delivered according to different models. For the purposes of this Directive, the term ‘cloud computing services’ covers services that allow access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable computing resources. Those computing resources include resources such as networks, servers or other infrastructure, storage, applications and services. The term ‘scalable’ refers to computing resources that are flexibly allocated by the cloud service provider, irrespective of

⁶We recognize that this is **not** an exhaustive list of regulations and directives that may be of concern for the Dellingr project.

the geographical location of the resources, in order to handle fluctuations in demand. The term ‘elastic pool’ is used to describe those computing resources that are provisioned and released according to demand in order to rapidly increase and decrease resources available depending on workload. The term ‘shareable’ is used to describe those computing resources that are provided to multiple users who share a common access to the service, but where the processing is carried out separately for each user, although the service is provided from the same electronic equipment.

The directive concerns the network and information security and affect the Dellingr framework in the capacity of facilitating access to resources.

The **eIDAS regulation** concerns the electronic identification and trust services that are necessary to ensure the eligibility of Service Consumers and to establish the trust chain necessary for the service exchange.

The **General Data Protection Regulation** concerns the rights of the Service Consumers, its implications for the Dellingr framework are similar to the implications for the eduGAIN inter-federation service as documented in Milestone M9.2 of the GN4-2 project [13].

11 Recommendations

The first recommendation is to use inter-federations, such as eduGAIN, alongside national federations. The inter-federation would replace email-based registration, which is in use in Denmark, Finland, Norway and Iceland. The usage of an inter-federation for Authentication does not mean that anybody with e.g. eduGAIN could register an account. Organizations may be blacklisted or whitelisted, and it is possible to require manual approval for some organizations. The benefit of using an inter-federation would be to make registration process easier and the users’ identities stronger. The next step would be to use a (legal) electronic identity in conjunction with an identity provided through an inter-federation. An eIDAS-compliant service would provide a strong identity of a users and their membership in an organization would be proven via an identity inter-federation.

The second recommendation is to integrate a group management service, such as Cesnet Perun or Internet2 coManage, so that projects and resources could be managed centrally. Experience gained by the NeIC Glenna project should be analyzed and taken into consideration.

The third recommendation is to ensure that all participating entities have all required agreements in place, particularly with the appropriate regulations in mind. The agreements should encompass both the requirements for network and information security as well as requirements for GDPR compliance, electronic identification and trust services. It may be appropriate to provide a template for the legal agreements but this might be outside of the scope of the Dellingr project.

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